

Automated IR image Segmentation For Identification Of Overheated Idlers In Belt Conveyor Systems Based On Outlier-Detection Method

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Abstract

Conveying systems play an essential role in the continuous horizontal transportation of raw materials in mining sites. Regular inspections of conveyor system structures and their components, especially idlers, are essential for proper maintenance. Traditional inspection methods are labor-intensive and hazardous. This paper proposes an automated method to determine overheated idlers. Input data is infrared (IR) and RGB videos of a conveyor system from a mobile robot. Such videos contain disturbances (e.g. sun reflections) which create difficulties to the segmentation of overheated idlers. The method is based on the outliers detection technique. Values of outliers in 8-bit grayscale histogram of extracted frames were considered as optimal threshold values. For the performance validation the shapes and locations of segmented hot spots were compared with RGB frames from the same scene. Furthermore, the segmentation results of four different global thresholding methods have been compared to the proposed method.

Keywords: Overheated idlers detection; Maintenance; Inspection robots; IR image; Outlier detection

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1. Introduction

Conveyors have been developed and used as the most common system for conveying all forms of material in the mining industry. For decades conveyors have been used for transporting raw materials due to their efficiency and relatively straightforward design. Despite the conveyor advantages, there are still significant challenges for conducting regular inspections to guarantee their operation under harsh environmental conditions in mines [1–5].

Idlers are important parts of the conveyors that support the belt to carry the material along its full length [6, 7]. Idlers can be damaged by friction, tear, wear, jamming, or seizure. Faulty idlers can become overheated and cause belt damage, thus the temperature, noise emissions, and vibrations of the idler should be constantly monitored through regular inspections. Idlers are located along the conveyor and the typical length of conveyors in the mining tunnel could reach several kilometers [8]. Human inspection of idlers by walking along the belt is time-consuming, costly, and hazardous as even a small conveyor of 150 meters consists of nearly 450 carrying rollers and 50 return rollers that should be inspected individually [9]. Monitoring the surface temperature of idlers is a key for finding faulty idlers because the abnormal temperature rise is an important characterization of idlers failure on conveyors.

Another critical issue in this particular application is the size of the conveyor. As mentioned, it may be 100m or even 1000m with a large number of idlers to check on a regular basis. The idea of this paper is to provide a quick and simple method to collect (inspection robot, see [10–13]) and process (the core of this paper) IR images to identify serious problems with overheated idlers.

Several types of faults and conditions in rotating machinery such as coupling looseness, rotor imbalance, misalignment, rolling element bearing damage, and lubricant inadequacy can be detected in the IR image [2, 10, 14, 15]. Although the single infrared image obtained by the infrared camera is widely used for fault detection in rotating machines, usually the infrared image has fewer details, low contrast, and lower resolution compared to RGB images, which makes them not suitable for accurate fault detection [16]. Therefore in this paper, we propose to use both RGB and IR images that are captured from the conveyor.

Image segmentation is a fundamental step in IR image analysis and it remains a challenge under adverse environmental conditions. Adverse environmental conditions in our case can be defined as the existence of reflective objects that can reflect sunlight or the appearance of other hot elements alongside the conveyor[17]. For addressing the mentioned issues and increasing the accuracy of the image segmentation process in this paper we proposed two solutions.

30 The first solution consists of defining a region of interest (ROI) on extracted key-frames from IR video to minimize the number of hot objects that can be wrongly detected as overheated idlers. Through our examination, we found out that even after the definition of the ROI, a considerable number of potential artifacts were still existing on extracted key frames. Therefore, as a second solution, we proposed an image segmentation method that worked based on the interquartile range (IQR) outliers detection technique. The proposed methods can accurately detect the overheated idlers even in the presence of potential artifacts. Finally, For validation of segmentation results, locations and shapes of the segmented hot spots are compared with time-synchronized RGB frames that were taken from the same point of view by the mobile robot.

35 The paper is organized as follows. First, the problem becomes increasingly explored (as predictive maintenance and inspection robotics are discussed by many authors), thus a comprehensive literature review is provided. It has been divided into several paragraphs as a few perspectives need to be mentioned. Then, an original procedure for overheated idler detection is proposed. Next, we describe the experimental trials and data acquired by the inspection robot in the real environment, and finally, the results of the proposed methodology applied to real data are presented and discussed.

2. Literature review

45 For ensuring the safe and most cost-effective operation of industrial machines, regular inspection should be performed by human operators, advanced monitoring systems (SCADAs) [18, 19] or recently also by inspection mobile robots [10, 12, 20].

Critical infrastructures are almost always equipped with many sensors and supervisory systems. However, in some situations, as is considered in this paper, condition monitoring systems can be applied on a limited scale only. Drive units (engine, gearbox, etc.) are usually monitored by SCADA[21]. But the rest of the conveyors (for example, a typical conveyor is 1km length), namely moving belt, hundreds of rotating idlers, etc. are difficult to monitor by stationary installation [22]. Hence, they are inspected by maintenance staff. Unfortunately, the mining environment is very harsh for that reason, there is a general tendency to minimize the presence of humans. Consequently, the place for the inspection robot is created.

2.1. Mobile robotics for infrastructure inspection

55 Inspection robotics becomes a rapidly growing technology, so the number of papers related to using drones (UAV), MAVs [23–27], UGV [11, 28] or legged robots [12, 29, 30] increase every year [23, 25, 31]. Inspection robotics for mining applications is a specific ones, which can be used for exploration, reclamation [25], rescue actions[32], predictive maintenance [11, 28], etc.

60 Regarding the advantages of mobile robots in mining sites, in [20] researchers discussed the reasons that make robotics systems a proper choice for conducting regular inspections in harsh places like deep underground mines. Similarly, in [33], the authors discussed the risks that can treat miners in coal mines and proposed solutions based on the application of autonomous mobile robots in inspection missions.

In recent years, a considerable number of researches have been published regarding the application of mobile robots for condition monitoring of industrial infrastructures in mines. The work of [10] introduced an unmanned ground vehicle robot for inspection of the belt conveyor system. The proposed robot is controlled by a human operator and uses infrared tomography techniques to identify temperature anomalies in conveyor belt systems. In their next paper [11] they developed an automatic robot-based inspection system for 3D modeling and path planning in mines. In [34] researchers proposed a robotics platform for fire identification based on a fusion of data from IR camera, temperature, and smoke sensors. The work of [35] proposed an inspection robotics program for monitoring of the key transmission components temperatures in a conveyor system.

2.2. IR thermography's application to industrial infrastructure inspections

75 The IR image can be used for detecting temperature anomalies in industrial infrastructures. More recent work has proposed the application of IR image processing in condition monitoring of industrial infrastructures. In [36] researchers are developed a method for condition monitoring of rotating machineries using thermal image processing. The authors, discussed about the advantages of thermal image based machine health monitoring over the vibration

monitoring methods. The proposed method used a convolutional neural network to extract and classify the features for identifying faults in captured IR images. Similar to Jia et al., [37] investigated a fault detection method using infrared IR images for identifying the air compressor pipeline leakage in a mining site. An image processing method for detecting the abnormal heat in underground mine car proposed by [38].

80 IR and RGB images fusion have been commonly proposed in a wide range of problems related to inspection robotics. The image captured by multiple sensors such as thermal, ultraviolet, and RGB cameras can be used for identification and validation of faults in industrial infrastructures [39]. In this context, [40] presented a multisensor information fusion system based on the back propagation neural network (BPNN) for controlling a fire-fighting Inspection robot. In [41], the authors developed a state-of-the-art computer vision methods to identify damaged
85 equipment in power transmission lines. Researchers in [42] proposed a method based on the fusion of the RGB and IR images for leakage detection in transmission pipes using a deep learning method.

2.3. Hot spot as an outlier - outlier detection methods

Even if inspection robotics becomes increasingly popular, the analysis of data acquired by a robot is still challenging. In this section, we will discuss IR image processing and analysis for hot spot detection with a particular focus
90 on industrial (mining) applications. The general idea is based on extraction areas in IR images with relatively higher temperatures in compared to other areas, so a threshold value is required.

During the measurements, the inspection robot was able to capture the sequence of IR images without information about the true temperature of the conveyor elements. Due to the automatic scaling of colors to the temperature range, "hard" thresholding based on the predefined value of temperature was not possible. The novel idea here exploits the
95 concept of outliers. If in a given IR image any hot element will appear in the distribution of pixels, the right tail related to "hot" colors will be heavier than for "normal temperature" elements. Our target is to detect really hot elements in the conveyor, i.e., significantly higher temperature than other elements in the picture. Thus, our detection strategy was focused on outlier detection in the distribution of pixel color values. Outlier detection is a well-known problem in statistics, data mining, and various applications. Deep reviews one may find in [43–48]

100 2.4. IR Image segmentation methods - state of the art

To evaluate the performance of proposed segmentation method, four different auto thresholding methods, namely, Minimum method, Interodes, Yen, and Rényi entropy, were applied to our IR image data set.

The Interodes method is worked based on the assumption that the optimal threshold can be founded in bimodal or multimodal histogram as a minimum. It is supposed that the segmented objects are created and a maximum
105 occurs around the most frequent grey level value in an image histogram [49]. Similarly to the internodes, the minimum method assumes a bimodal histogram. In this method, the histogram is smoothed until only two local maxima remain[49]. The Yen's method is a multilevel thresholding algorithm that takes into account two factors, the disparity between the thresholded images of the original ones and the number of bits required for the representation of the thresholded image [50]. In the Rényi entropy method, the optimal threshold value is defined based on extraction of
110 distributions probabilities of background and object extracted from the grey level distribution of original image [51].

3. Automatic procedure for overheated idler detections based on IR Video analysis collected by the inspection robot

3.1. General concept

Segmentation techniques are useful for the separation of objects of interest from their backgrounds [52]. As shown
115 in Fig.1, to achieve an accurate segmentation of overheated idlers, the following steps were performed: the proposed method starts by loading the infrared IR video and extracting the Key-frames. Through the data collection, we received a set of pictures containing many non-informative components related to the conveyor infrastructure. Therefore, in the next step, an ROI is defined on the extracted Key-frames based on the idea proposed by [53]. Afterward, the 24-bit color-coded IR images were converted to 8-bit grayscale image before performing the segmentation process as the
120 proposed thresholding method, requires an 8-bit grayscale image as input. In the next step, the grey scaled histogram of the preprocessed IR images were extracted and the outliers values were defined based on the IQR technique. Finally, the optimal threshold value is defined based on the value of the extracted outliers.

For validation of the segmentation results, the location of identified hotspots in segmented frames are compared to RGB images that are captured from a same point of view. Time synchronization is required for integration of data from RGB an IR camera therefore RGB an IR images are synchronized to be compared based on the same time reference. Furthermore to match the image resolution of the RGB to IR images the similar ROI are defined over original captured RGB images. This was necessary, since different camera models with differing image resolutions were used by the inspection robot.

Figure 1: The Structure of the proposed method.

3.2. Key-frame extraction from captured IR video

Through the conducted examination, the mobile robot continuously record the thermal videos from the conveyor, therefore, many frames are almost repeated in a certain time interval. Processing a large number of repeated frames would unnecessarily increase the amount of computational power that is necessary for the segmentation process.

Keyframe extraction is a method for expressing the important contents of a captured video file by extracting an important frames [54]. Sampling-Based technique is a method for selecting key frames by uniformly or randomly extracting important frames from the original captured video [55]. This method works based on the idea of choosing every K^{th} frame from the original video. The value of the K parameter can be defined depending on the duration of the video. Usually, from 5% to 15% of the whole video is summarized for extracting key frames. The experimental results show that summarization of 10% video or extraction of every 10th frame gave us enough information to express the main content of the video concisely and reduce the redundant information of the video data [56].

3.3. Pre-Segmentation of IR image - cropping / selection of ROI for further analysis

Considering the size of IR images (resolution of 640x480), it would be advantageous if redundant data in non-idlers region can be removed. This reduction has to be performed in a way such that no idlers data is lost while, computational burden is reduced. Therefore, for reducing the amount of unrelated information, an ROI is defined on the original IR frames based on the assumption that IR camera point was remained approximately unchanged during the conducted exam fig. 2.

Figure 2: Selection of ROI on the captured IR images

3.4. Segmentation of hot spots based on outliers detection technique

The proposed segmentation method, worked based on the fact that in IR images with uniform background, the number of pixels belonging to background or cold areas are much larger than the number of pixels belonging to foreground or overheated objects. Therefore, the foreground representing hot spots will lie at the upper boundary of IR images 8-bit grayscale histogram.

Outlier detection is a problem of finding patterns in data that are not in the range of normal behavior. In this paper, hot spots in IR images are considered anomalous patterns and treated as outliers. IQR is a technique that helps to find outliers in the data which are continuously distributed. IQR is the difference between the first quartile and the third quartile: $IQR = Q3 - Q1$. In this method, an image histogram is divided into four parts, first, second, and third quartiles Eq. 1 where N is number of samples.

$$\text{First quartile } (Q1) = ((n + 1)/4)^{th} \text{ Term}$$

$$\text{Second quartile } (Q2) = ((n + 1)/2)^{th} \text{ Term} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Third quartile } (Q3) = (3(n + 1)/4)^{th} \text{ Term}$$

The schematic boxplot is divided data based on four invisible boundaries: two inner fences and two outer fences. The lower inner fence, is computed as $Q1 - 1.5 IQR$ and upper inner fence, is $Q3 + 1.5 IQR$. The, upper and lower part of outer fences can be defines as $Q1 - 3 IQR$ and $Q3 + 3 IQR$, respectively. The mild outliers can be classifies as values that are beyond lower and upper inner fence while extreme outliers are assigned to values that are beyond either lower or upper outer fences [57]. Through examination, we found out that overheated idlers cannot always define as mild outliers. Accordingly, for increasing the chance of true detection, the value of extreme outliers are extracted for each frame and considered as an optimal threshold value for segmenting of the overheated idlers Fig 3.

Figure 3: Comparison of mild and extreme outlier detection results in segmentation of overheated idlers

4. Experiments

The experiment has been done in real mining conditions. During the inspection mission, the robotic platform controlled by the operator has captured various types of data including RGB images, IR images, sound, lidar data, etc., for various diagnostic tasks, see Fig. 4. Here we will discuss only RGB/IR images. The main parameters of cameras are frames per second, 25fps, resolution of 640x480. The cameras observation angle was 40 degrees, they has been installed on the robot at the height of 100cm above the ground floor.

Considered belt conveyor has been in operation in an industrial hall with mineral resource storage, see Fig. 5. The parameters of the conveyors are as follows: length - 150m, belt width - 0.8m, idler spacing - 1.45m, idler diameter 133mm.

Figure 4: A general picture of the raw materials storage with belt conveyor to transport raw materials.

Figure 5: View of the robot during inspection.

During the measurements, several data acquisition sessions have been performed. It is worthy to notice that the environmental conditions are time-varying (even if it is in a kind of indoor condition). A critical issue is that during the experiment, the true temperature of the conveyor elements and IR camera automatically adjust the colors to a given

175 temperature range that it produces many complicated images. Based on the manual analysis of the acquired data, we have selected several interesting situations that could be problematic during automatic image analysis. Below we present some of such "difficult to analyze" pictures. In general, one may group them into several classes, namely: images without hot idler, images with hot idler, images with sunlight reflection without hot idler, images with sunlight reflection with hot idler, etc, see the examples presented below Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Four classes of images that were difficult to analyze

180 5. Application to real data

In this section, we will present examples of partial results: raw images, detection results for several images mentioned above. The purpose of this section is to present how difficult is the application of IR image analysis for industrial data, especially in the mining industry.

185 In Fig. 7, one can notice that in the raw IR images there are many non-informative (from the hot idler detection perspective) areas related to, for example, windows or sunlight reflection on the belt (marked by arrows). This will make image processing difficult and this is the main reason to limit analyzed area to conveyor related only (cropping the image). In Fig. 8 one can see another example of hot spots (marked by frames) not related to idlers. It shows that the application to real industrial data is always difficult due to unpredictable sources of noise/unwanted components.

Figure 7: location of sunlight sources and sun reflations on belt that captured in a raw IR image

Figure 8: Examples of hot spots that are not related to idlers

In Fig. 9 there is an example of IR image with a hot idler with some minor sunlight reflection on the part of the belt. Objects with a low emissivity value like reflective objects can reflect the IR radiations strongly [58]. Notice that the belt surface is black, smooth, and shiny that makes a very probable sunlight reflection problem. Therefore, the IR camera is measured the reflected temperature instead of measuring the temperature of the object itself. For instance belt surface might be the same temperature as an adjacent object but appear much hotter.

In result, the methodology will provide false detection of sunlight recognised as a hot area. Examples presented here with a detailed discussion on the detection efficiency and understanding of the source of the problem are necessary before automatic processing of hundreds of images. In the next sections, we will discuss the global efficiency with some indicators of detection quality. Even if there are some problematic examples hard to recognize, other known techniques appear much less efficient. Moreover, the proposed technique is automatic and provides results in an objective way that is better than the subjective opinion performed by experts.

(a) Preprocessed key frame

(b) Segmented frame

(c) RGB image captured from the same scene

Figure 9: Example of frames that sunlight reflection and overheated idler were segmented at the same time

200 **6. Results**

The discussed method in this paper is tested on an image data set that was captured from the left side of a conveyor by a mobile robot. All frames were captured during the real case scenario where the robot was constantly moving along the conveyor. The data set consists of 5370 frames and 86 different idlers were fully recognized on both sides of the conveyor. Through the segmentation process, 537 key-frames were chosen to process.

205 **6.1. Validation of detection results based on manual analysis**

The performance of the proposed method in the segmentation of overheated idlers is evaluated through the visual interpretation process. By consideration of the number of thermal sources that can be detected as an overheated idler alongside the conveyor, validation of the segmentation results is important. For example, as a showman in Fig. 10, in different cases, hot objects are wrongly segmented as overheated idlers. Therefore, through the validation process, 210 the shape and location of the segmented hotspots in segmented frames were compared to RGB images.

Figure 10: Example of frames that presence of overheated idlers were hard to validate

6.2. Accuracy comparison of the discussed segmentation techniques

The performance of the proposed method is compared to other segmentation methods based on the recognition theory: sensitivity and specificity.

In this paper true positive (TP) is referred to the frames where overheated idlers were correctly segmented. In other 215 hand, false positive (FP) is represents the number of frames where other thermal sources were wrongly segmented as

overheated idlers. The proportion of true positives cases that are correctly identified by proposed method is defined by the sensitivity or true positive rate (TPR) Eq. 2.

$$TPR = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (2)$$

In this paper, true negative cases (TN) is referred to the to the frames where no overheated idler was neither present nor detected. Whereas false negative (FN) can be described as the number of frames where faulty idlers were not segmented due to the underestimation. The proportion of the true negatives that correctly identified by a method is described by the specificity or the true negative rate (TNR) Eq. 3,. The TNR define how good the method is at identifying normal (negative) cases.

$$TNR = \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \quad (3)$$

Accuracy (ACC) shows the proportion of true results, either true positive or true negative cases. ACC is defined by Eq. 4, where TP and TN represent the same parts of the data that were described in sensitivity and specificity and N represents the total number of processed frames.

$$ACC = \frac{TP + TN}{N} \quad (4)$$

The summarized results of the performance of each method based on the described factors are proposed in Table 1.

Table 1: Comparison of proposed method performances in segmentation of overheated idlers

Method	TP	TN	FP	FN	TPR	TNR	ACC
IQR method (Extreme outliers)	117	360	48	12	0.90	0.88	0.88
IQR method (Mid outliers)	121	183	233	0	1	0.43	0.56
Minimum method	104	0	433	0	1	0	0.19
Intermodes	71	0	466	0	1	0	0.13
Yen	50	0	487	0	1	0	0.09
Rényi entropy	15	0	522	0	1	0	0.02

7. Discussion

Based on the data represented in Table 1, IQR (extreme outliers) method could correctly segmented the faulty idler 88% of the time. The IQR method (mid outliers) by 52% accuracy has the best performance in the next place. Furthermore, the minimum thresholding method could only segment the overheated idlers in 19% percent of the time. The most ineffective and undesired results were delivered by intermodes, Yen, and Rényi entropy methods. In general, they could only be effective between 2% to 10% of the time.

The proposed method could successfully detect faulty idlers in 127 frames and wrongly detect other thermal sources overheated idlers in 40 frames. In another word, the proposed method could successfully detect 26 overheated idlers and missed to detect 4 overheated idlers. The algorithm was especially inefficient with incorrect detection of the overheated hot spots in the presence of sun reflection on the belt. In those cases, the number of invalid results raised significantly.

Fig. 11 compared the performance factors of proposed method on processed key-frames. As it is show by FP factor, a potential issue that is not handled by the proposed method were specially raised in the last part of the analyzed video where the presence of sun light reflection over belt is increased.

Figure 11: Comparison of performance factors in processed frames.

8. Conclusions

Thermal imaging has been widely used for the inspection of industrial infrastructures since they are beneficial tools in regular inspection applications. In this work, an inspection procedure for conveyor systems maintenance has been proposed with a particular focus on overheated idler detection. Furthermore, a method of automatic hot spot detection is proposed. The designed method worked based on the idea of consideration of hot spots as outliers.

The method has been tested on a real data set, namely, IR images acquired from mining companies have been analyzed in the context of detection of hot spots related to overheated idlers. As the experiment has been done in a real harsh environment typical to the mining reality, there are some extreme examples of images difficult to recognize. However, the global efficiency of the method was more than 88%, where 86 different idlers were recognized through the inspection process. After the segmentation and validation process, 26 overheated idlers were recognized, while our proposed method missed to detect 4 overheated idlers. Afterward, for validation of the proposed and other compared algorithms, the result of the discussed methods has been compared to the RGB images captured by mobile robots. The method has been compared with other automatic thresholding techniques based on the recognition theory: sensitivity and specificity. Through the comparison procedure, we determine that the performance is generally 70 percent better than the compared methods. It should be mentioned that the conveyor should be inspected on a regular basis. Substitution of maintenance staff with the mobile robotic platform and automatic procedures for image processing is really helpful. Even if the analysis of images will return some suspicious results for some cases, it may be validated by experienced staff in the office. We also plan to fuse RGB and IR images as according to our experience, the sunlight reflection is mostly related to the belt surface. If one can recognize the belt from the RGB image, the location of the hot spot on the IR image may be combined with the location of the belt/idler, and the detection result can be accepted or rejected. This concept was preliminarily discussed in laboratory conditions [10] but needs to be deeply studied and tested in the real environment.

Further research will be conducted to improve the accuracy of the method in terms of adaptability to rapid changes in environmental parameters like temperature. Furthermore, future experiments are planned on a larger population of conveyors in different mining sites. It is also planned to link the results of IR and RGB images results with data from the robot's lidar localization system for accurate localization of overheated idlers in Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) denied environments like deep underground mines.

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Data Availability Statement

Archived data sets cannot be accessed publicly according to the NDA agreement signed by the authors.

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conflictsofinterest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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